

Effect of flooding duration on germination and growth of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Alley cropping of green manure with irrigated rice could save time and crop area. We conducted a pot culture experiment Jan-Mar 1989 to study the effect of six irrigation schedules on germination and growth of *S. rostrata*.

Pots were filled with Vertisol to 5 cm from the brim. Seeds treated with sulfuric acid for 40 min were sown at 25/pot. Six treatments were imposed with three replications. The crop was grown for 65 d.

Germination was drastically

Influence of irrigation on germination and dry matter production of *Sesbania rostrata*. Dharwad, India, 1989.

Treatment	Plants/pot (no.)	Germination (%)	Shoot dry weight (g/pot)	Root dry weight (g/pot)	Total dry weight (g/pot)
Control (no flooding)	20.3	81.2	5.05	0.51	5.56
Flooding throughout	5.6	22.4	0.23	0.04	0.27
Flooding 7 d after sowing (DAS)	10.6	42.4	1.42	0.13	1.55
Flooding 15 DAS	16.3	65.2	2.51	1.03	3.54
Flooding 22 DAS	18.6	74.4	3.03	1.18	4.21
Flooding 30 DAS	18.0	72.0	4.00	1.21	5.21
SE±	2.0		0.32	0.032	0.34
LSD (P=0.05)	6.4		1.00	0.100	1.08

reduced when irrigation started immediately after sowing (see table). Flooding 22 days after sowing (DAS) did not affect germination significantly. Shoot dry weight significantly decreased with continuous flooding but increased with delay in flooding. Flooding 30 DAS did not significantly

affect total dry matter production. *S. rostrata* could be established as an alley crop with rice if irrigation is delayed to 15 DAS. For better establishment and dry matter production, the green manure crop should not be flooded before 30 DAS. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of herbicides on nutrient leaching from rice leaves

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Pesticidal spray is known to alter the constituents of leaf leachates, which in turn have a direct effect on disease incidence, yield, and yield quality. Certain fungicides are known to induce leaching of different micronutrients. We studied the effect of thiobencarb and butachlor on leaching of Na, K, and Fe from rice leaves.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications during 1987 wet season. Saket 4 was seeded and recommended fertilizers and irrigation practices were followed. Thiobencarb and butachlor at 1.5 kg/ha were sprayed 3 d after seeding as preemergence herbicide. Control plots were not sprayed.

Rice leaf samples were collected 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 d after emergence (DE). Leaf leachates were collected by

Effect of herbicides on nutrients in rice leaf leachates. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	10 DE	15 DE	20 DE	25 DE	30 DE
<i>Na (g/kg fresh leaves)</i>					
Control	10.9	15.0	15.5	14.7	15.9
Thiobencarb	13.0	16.8	19.6	14.9	17.0
Butachlor	11.9	15.5	15.5	15.5	17.6
LSD (0.05)	0.8	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.5
<i>K (g/kg fresh leaves)</i>					
Control	30.0	38.4	43.6	42.7	43.5
Thiobencarb	45.3	47.8	49.1	58.3	61.5
Butachlor	43.1	46.6	52.0	53.9	58.4
LSD (0.05)	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.8	2.1
<i>Fe (g/kg fresh leaves)</i>					
Control	2.8	2.5	3.6	3.6	4.5
Thiobencarb	4.9	5.0	6.9	6.5	6.8
Butachlor	4.4	5.8	6.5	7.5	7.2
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3

immersing freshly collected leaves in distilled water for about 6 h. Free Fe content was estimated using potassium persulphate reagent, Na and K content by Flame photometer method.

Nutrients in leaf leachates increased from 10 to 30 DE in untreated and treated leaves (see table). Na content increased between 10 and 20 DE, decreased at 25 DE, and increased again at 30 DE.

Herbicides significantly increased Na, K, and Fe content. Application of thiobencarb resulted in more leaching of Na at 10, 15, and 20 DE; K at 10, 25, and 30 DE; and Fe at 10 and 20 DE. Application of butachlor resulted in more leaching of Na at 25 and 30 DE; K at 20 DE; and Fe at 15, 2.5, and 30 DE. At 15 and 20 DE, the differences in leaching of K due to thiobencarb and butachlor were not significant. □